

Optically Active Tertiary Alcohols containing Asymmetric Center in sec-Butyl Group

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Optically active tertiary alcohols of the type $R_2\overset{\text{OH}}{\underset{\text{CH}_3}{\text{C}}}-\text{CH}.\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ have been obtained by the action of ethyl (+)-1-methylbutyrate on different Grignard complexes, RMgX , where $\text{R} = \text{Me}, \text{Et}, \text{Pr}^n, \text{Pr}^i, \text{Bu}^n$ or Bi^i . The optical rotations of these alcohols have been studied, the maximum rotation was with (-)-1 : 1-diethyl 2-methyl butan-1-ol, and minimum rotation with (-)-1 : 1-diisopropyl 2-methyl butanol-1-ol.

Frankland and Twiss¹, Roger and McKay², and Thaker and Vasi³ obtained optically active glycols by the action of Grignard complexes on the esters of optically active hydroxy-acids. These glycols of the type $\text{R}.\overset{*}{\text{C}}(\text{OH}).\text{C}(\text{OH}).\text{R}'_2$, where R is from optically active hydroxy-acid and R' from Grignard complex, have only one asymmetric carbon atom in their molecules. Thaker and Pathak⁴ prepared optically active tertiary alcohols by condensing (+)-2-methyl butylethyl acetate with various Grignard reagents wherein $-\text{CO}_2\text{R}'$ group is involved in condensation with Grignard complex. Their findings agreed with the conclusions of Grignard⁵⁻⁷ and Boyd and Hatt⁸ that when the reacting ester is from an optically active carboxylic acid the resulting tertiary alcohol is optically active.

However, Bergmann and Hartrott⁹ obtained optically inactive 1 : 1-diphenyl 2-methyl pentan-1-ol from methyl ester of (-)-1-methyl-butane 1-carboxylic acid and phenyl magnesium bromide. To explain this inactivity Campbell and Kenyon¹⁰ suggested that the carbinol formed undergoes spontaneous reversible dehydration, resulting in the loss of activity:

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8. D. R. Boyd and H. H. Hatt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 898.
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Also, the formation of inactive product with racemisation is possible, if in the optically active ester, the $-\text{CO}_2\text{R}'$ group is attached directly to the asymmetric carbon atom. However, the authors also obtained optically active (+) tertiary alcohols from (–) methylhydratropate and methyl and phenyl Grignard complex, wherein $-\text{CO}_2\text{R}'$ group is attached to the asymmetric carbon atom. On similar lines, the authors undertook the condensation of ethyl (+)-1-methylbutyrate and Grignard complexes when active tertiary alcohols were obtained. In this work the ester contains $-\text{CO}_2\text{R}'$ group attached to asymmetric carbon atom, and unlike the previous authors (–) tertiary alcohols resulted from ethyl (+)-1-methylbutyrate.

The optically active tertiary alcohols obtained by the action of ethyl (+)-1-methylbutyrate and Grignard reagent, RMgX , in which R represents methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, isopropyl, *n*-butyl and isobutyl are 1 : 1 : 2-trimethyl butan-1-ol, 1 : 1-diethyl 2-methyl butan-1-ol, 1 : 1-di-*n*-propyl 2-methyl butan-1-ol, 1 : 1-diisopropyl 2-methyl butan-1-ol, 1 : 1-di-*n*-butyl 2-methyl butan-1-ol and 1 : 1-diisobutyl 2-methyl butan-1-ol respectively. The optical rotations of these carbinols have been recorded and it seems there is an irregularity in molecular rotations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl (+)-1-methylbutyrate : Mixture of (+)-1-methylbutyric acid (100 g.; b.p. 172–73°; $[\alpha]_D^{23} +4.15$), ethyl alcohol (150 ml.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2 ml.) was refluxed for 4.5 hrs. The reaction mixture was poured into excess water, washed several times with water, followed by saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, water and dried with anhydrous magnesium sulphate and distilled. Ethyl (+)-1-methylbutyrate distilled at 133–135°: Yield 74%; $d_4^{25} 0.9404$; $n_D^{25} 1.397$; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +4.10$ (1, 1). (Found : C, 64.08; H, 10.25. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 64.63; H, 10.76%).

General Method for the Preparation of Optically Active Tertiary Alcohols : Ethyl (+)-1-methylbutyrate (65.0 g.; 0.5 mole) dissolved in absolute dry ether (90 ml.) was added dropwise during 2 hrs to an ethereal solution of Grignard reagent prepared from magnesium (1 mole), alkyl halide (1 mole) and ether about 270 ml. It was then decomposed with ice and saturated solution of ammonium chloride, the ethereal layer separated, washed with water, then with sodium hydroxide (5%) solution and finally with water. On drying (sodium sulphate) and evaporation of ether, the residual carbinol distilled under vacuum. Yields, boiling point, optical rotations and molecular rotations are recorded in Table I.

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TABLE I

No.	Name	R	B.P. (20 mm) °C	Yield (%)	d_4^{32}	n_D^{32}	$[\alpha]_D^{32}$ (1, 1)	Molecular Rotation	Molecular Formula	Found %	Required %
1.	(-)-1 : 1 : 2-Trimethyl butan-1-ol	Methyl	57-58	77.5	0.9187	1.412	-2.72	-315.6	C ₇ H ₁₆ O	C, 72.87 H, 13.18	C, 72.41 H, 13.79
2.	(-)-1 : 1-Diethyl-2-methyl butan-1-ol	Ethyl	70-71	33.3	0.9241	1.430	-2.98	-429.1	C ₉ H ₂₀ O	C, 74.23 H, 13.63	C, 74.99 H, 13.89
3.	(-)-1 : 1-Di- <i>n</i> -Propyl-2-methyl butan-1-ol	<i>n</i> -Propyl	80-90	33.0	0.9264	1.433	-1.91	-328.5	C ₁₁ H ₂₄ O	C, 76.88 H, 13.45	C, 76.76 H, 13.95
4.	(-)-1 : 1-Diisopropyl-2-methyl butan-1-ol	Iso-propyl	75-80	25.5	0.9281	1.429	-0.52	-89.43	C ₁₁ H ₂₄ O	C, 76.37 H, 13.81	C, 76.76 H, 13.95
5.	(+)-1 : 1-Di- <i>n</i> -butyl-2-methyl butan-1-ol	<i>n</i> -Butyl	150-155	55.0	0.8945 (30°)	1.435 (30°)	+1.31 (30°)	+262.0	C ₁₃ H ₂₈ O	C, 77.78 H, 13.92	C, 78.00 H, 14.00
6.	(+)-1 : 1-Diisobutyl-2-methyl butan-1-ol	Iso-butyl	135-142	38.0	0.9128 (30°)	1.424 (30°)	+0.66 (30°)	+132.0	C ₁₃ H ₂₈ O	C, 78.02 H, 13.82	C, 78.00 H, 14.00

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